

DEVELOPMENT OF ISLAMIC BANKING IN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Annotation: Islamic finance (Islamic Bank) is basically a financial system that complies with Islamic religious laws. Over the past decades, it has become an industry of 2.1 trillion dollars with assets expected to grow to 3.4 trillion dollars by the end of 2018. With this potential, the global financial community is actively exploring opportunities in this area. In this article, opinions and comments will be made about the share of Islamic banks in European countries.

Keywords: European countries, Islamic finance, banking activities, income, honesty, economic stability.

At a time when economic uncertainty is rising, the Islamic Bank appears to be one of several selected financial sectors where forecasts remain optimistic. The reason for this is three in the structural principles of operations, they offer a completely different view to the boom-bust cycles, which eventually led to the economic train crash of the 2008 year.

But what is Islamic banking? What makes it different from other banking and investment institutions?

The following points reflect some key elements of banking practice:

The Islamic bank prohibits collecting interest for borrowed money. As a result, Islamic banks are very sensitive to market fluctuations and must implement effective risk management strategies—they have significantly more impact on the real economy than ordinary banks.

In terms of profit and loss, participants in the transaction share both the risks and rewards that can be attached to it. Excessive losses are minimized due to the avoidance of internal risks of banking practices.

There is a clear ban on speculation in Islamic banks. Although it is possible to take risks, it is allowed only when all terms and conditions are clearly known to all parties. In other words, there is a ban on confidential information—transparency is a central pillar in Islamic finance.

The Islamic Bank requires the use of asset support—each transaction must be material, related to the underlying asset, which further enhances the relationship between Islamic banks and the real economy.

This finding is probably based on the concept of profit and loss, as well as the strong link between Islamic finance and the Real economy—a bad blow during the economic crisis. At the same time, this points to the need to establish

stability and stability in the Islamic system. Similar issues come up with ethical investment, they have found different research, share several characteristics with Islamic finance, although the latter are more public-oriented. Finally, the big difference between traditional finance and Islamic finance can be found in the issue of monetary policy, whose scope of operations in the Western system is based on interest rates. This is clearly different from the Prohibition of interest payments established by Islamic laws. Consequently, special instruments are more widely deployed for monetary policy, corresponding to Sharia. Understand why Islamic instruments and principle in an open market economy introduction to traditional financing can be a long and uneven process problems like this. In fact, the installation of "Islamic windows" on traditional financial systems is often a preferred arrangement, especially in Europe.

Islamic finance, which accounts for the majority of the Islamic banking market in Europe, which is well-known in the Gulf states, as well as in the countries of Southeast Asia (Malaysia in particular), has progressed gradually since its inception in the early 1980s. the share of Europe as a region in global Islamic financial assets remains, according to 2014 year, the assets of the regional Islamic bank (with the exception of non-Islamic banking institutions) accounted for only 0,5 percent of the global Fund. Islamic funds, which reside in European jurisdictions, were slightly better accounted for 14.4 billion dollars in assets (2014) and 20% of sharia-compliant assets around the world. However, the figures are expected to increase rapidly, as financial regulators of a number of European countries – from Ireland to Malta to France – have given frames to facilitate the registration of sharia-compliant investment schemes.

An encouraging sign is the establishment of a global Islamic finance and Investment Group. The main objective of the group is to identify key global opportunities and challenges facing Islamic finance and ways to develop the Global Islamic finance market. The first meeting took place in London in 2014 year and highlighted the leading role of the capital of Great Britain in the development of Islamic financing in Europe.

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